

Mid term Assessment report

Housing: to Overcome Unstable
Situation in Europe (H:OUSE)

H:OUSE

H:OUSE Project | Mid-term Assessment Report

2026 – February

Iscte - Instituto Universitário de Lisboa, Portugal

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H:OUSE Project | Mid-term Assessment Report

WP6

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IL SESTANTE
Cooperativa Sociale

GLOCAL FACTORY

SECOND TREE
Planting Second Chances

Doras

Promoting and Protecting Human Rights

iscte

INSTITUTO
UNIVERSITÁRIO
DE LISBOA

ZRC SAZU

artemisszió
Interkulturális Alapítvány

Comune di Ravenna

Refugees
Welcome
Italia

Phase 1: key results & learnings

425

participants engaged

63

nationalities represented

81

new sponsors

1

The project surpassed its engagement and networking goals.

Broader and more diverse local networks than planned

Migrant & diaspora communities

Local authorities

NGOs

Private sector - still limited

2

A shift in how housing is understood

From individual problem → structural challenge

Urban policies

Discrimination

Housing market dynamics

State underperformance

The main impact of phase 1 was cultural: changing how communities, institutions and migrants understand the housing problem

3

Integration as an indirect pathway to housing

No integration = difficult access to housing

Language learning

Social Networks

Employment

Knowledge of rights

Integration significantly increases the chances of accessing housing

4

New dialogue spaces that did not exist before

Stable spaces with potential beyond the project

Migrants

Municipalities

Universities

Sponsors

NGOs

Manifestos and working groups

Knowledge sharing

The first phase of **H:OUSE** has generated practice-based **knowledge** about **housing accesibility for migrants and refugees**. One of the most significant findings is a **cultural shift** concerning the way in which participants came to **understand housing** over the course of the project. Participants across territories progressively moved toward **recognising housing difficulties as structural conditions** rooted in broader urban and political dynamics. Beyond individual change, several partners documented a shift toward **collective commitment**, reflected in the co-development of community manifestos, the establishment of permanent multi-stakeholder working groups, and the **consolidation of cross-sectoral alliances** with potential to continue beyond the project's duration.

A key enabler of this process has been the **diversity of the networks** developed throughout the project. Across territories, partners observed that diversity attracts diversity. The presence of actors from different sectors and profiles within the same space generates a pull effect, **drawing in stakeholders who would not have engaged in a more homogeneous setting**. Reaching this diversity required **adapted strategies**, including multilingual outreach, the involvement of community leaders as bridges to newly arrived migrants, and the creation of informal spaces for exchange alongside more structured activities.

The evidence from the first phase also points to a **close connection between networks, integration, and housing access**. **Stronger networks facilitate better integration, and better integration opens more housing pathways**; through language learning, access to employment, knowledge of rights, and the development of social networks. In this regard, it has become equally clear that ensuring **migrants move from a consultative role to becoming active participants** and co-designers of solutions is essential.

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Table 2. Objectives of the project

1. Introduction

The H:OUSE project (Housing: to overcome unstable situations in Europe) has reached its halfway stage, a crucial moment for reflection and for the development of a roadmap based on the insights gained to date. At this point, partners from six intervention territories have completed the first phase of implementation, generating a substantial body of practice-based knowledge on housing constraints, multi-stakeholder networking and innovative housing practices. This mid-term report synthesises these experiences to support informed decision-making for the remainder of the project.

In recent years, Europe has experienced an acute housing crisis, characterised by a sustained decline in affordability (Hick, Pomati and Stephens, 2025, p. 1079). This process is reflected in the rising housing effort rate, which highlights the growing gap between stagnating wages and rising housing prices, making it increasingly difficult for low and middle income households to access adequate housing (Arnerić, Kikerec and Skoko, 2024, p.49). The scale of this crisis is significant enough to be described by the European Parliament as “a crucial challenge of our time and one of the main concerns of our citizens” (European Parliament, 2026).

This disparity reflects the dynamics of European housing markets over recent decades, driven, on the one hand, by the progressive financialisation of the housing stock and, on the other, by its increasing integration into global capital flows (Ubarevičienė and Aidukaitė, 2026). This process of commodification has accelerated gentrification and socio-spatial segregation, while also contributing to growing inequality between owners and tenants and the concentration of wealth in residential assets (Corradi and Ghekière, 2025; Siatitsa et al., 2025), thereby contributing to a reduction in the supply of affordable accommodation.

The housing crisis particularly affects migrants and refugees, for whom access to housing is a key pillar of the integration process (Brown et al., 2022). Despite the recognition of housing as a fundamental right (Council of Europe, 1996, p.14), these communities face a set of additional and compounding obstacles, including a shortage of social housing, insufficient regulation of the private rental market, geographical dispersal, discrimination by landlords and letting agencies (Netto, 2011, p.290), and bureaucratic requirements, further exacerbating their vulnerability.

Against this backdrop, the present mid-term report evaluates the H:ouse project, which aims to address housing insecurity among migrants and refugees within the European context.

The mid-term report serves as a monitoring and evaluation tool for the H:OUSE project. It is designed to gather information on three key aspects of the project: participation and network connections, knowledge sharing, and housing solutions. Acts as a progress report that allows for the monitoring of ongoing activities, the analysis of implementation processes, the identification of emerging trends, the evaluation of possible adjustments, and the identification of constraints and obstacles during implementation, as well as the

detection of opportunities for improvement to ensure alignment with the project's objectives.

The H:OUSE project involves the following organisations: Second Tree (Greece); Artemisszió (Hungary); ZRC SAZU (Slovenia); Refugees Welcome Italia, Comune di Ravenna, and Il Sestante (Italy); and DORAS (Ireland). Among these, Glocal Factory (Italy) and ISCTE-IUL (Portugal) do not have an area of intervention.

Figure 1. Map of the entities that conform H:OUSE project

The general objective of the H:OUSE project is to promote, through the support of community sponsorship, the recognition of the right to housing for migrants as an essential first step to implement meaningful integration processes in host communities, through the systematisation and multiplication of the most effective CS practices, building on the Irish model and leveraging on all the successful experiences in the field in which the partners themselves have participated in recent years or with which they are most familiar.

Building upon the general objective of promoting housing as a fundamental right for migrants through community sponsorship (CS), the H:OUSE project sets forth the following specific objectives to ensure the effective implementation, scalability, and impact of CS practices in host communities:

1. Expand knowledge on the topic of Community Sponsorship, in order to explore and capitalize on the most successful experiences.
2. Expand and diversify the pool of sponsors and individuals directly involved in the support and integration of migrants and asylum seekers.
3. Support and empower local sponsor communities by consolidating a support structure that includes all those actors (public and private) that play a role of relevance, impact and decision-making around the dynamics of access to housing.
4. Develop and implement innovative and concrete housing solutions for people in need of international protection, through the establishment of the local multi-stakeholder groups.
5. Expand the number of Member States running CS programmes.

The project evaluation includes two reports: the present mid-term report and the final report, both of which aim to reflect the results achieved, the difficulties encountered and the lessons learned by the participants of the H:OUSE project.

The sections that follow examine each of these dimensions in turn. Section 2 describes the methodology and data-gathering process used across implementing territories. Section 3 analyses the network connections established, and the strategies employed to sustain them. Section 4 examines the knowledge-sharing activities carried out and their contribution to mutual learning. Section 5 consolidates the key insights on housing solutions generated through pilot activities. Finally, Section 6 presents the main learnings and a roadmap for the second phase of the project.

Figure 2. Pilot activity developed in Padua, Italy

2. Methodology and data collection

This section explains how data were collected and analysed across the implementing territories during the first phase of the H:OUSE project. It describes the methodological choices made, the tools employed, and the ways in which both quantitative and qualitative information were gathered to inform the findings presented in this report.

The mid-term report has been prepared based on the Impact Assessment Strategy, using a flexible methodological framework that allows for the application of different data collection methods according to the specificities of each context and local activities. The analysis draws on a follow-up template with a common set of questions, completed by project partners, as well as quantitative data recorded periodically in an Excel logbook. This process has been guided by shared methodological guidelines to ensure consistency across contributions.

The present report is based on the collection of qualitative and quantitative feedback on the activities developed across the different Work Packages of the project up to the end of January 2026, supported by a data collection by partners with implementing territories. This collective design made it possible to establish a common approach, ensuring comparability between territories, while offering the necessary flexibility to adapt to different local contexts. Each partner had the autonomy to select the most appropriate methods for collecting feedback, considering the cultural, social and territorial

H:OUSE Partner	Data collection method of the intervention territories
Second Tree (Ioannina, Greece)	Quantitative: surveys Qualitative: feedback during activities, qualitative questionnaires
Il Sestante (Padova, Italy)	Quantitative: surveys Qualitative: interviews, focus groups, group activities, participatory methodologies
Refugees Welcome Italia (Ravenna, Emilia-Romagna, Italy)	Qualitative: interviews, informal feedback during activities, one-to-one meetings, group work, participatory discussions
DORAS (Limerick, Ireland)	Qualitative: informal feedback during discussions on activities and future collaborations
Artemisszió (Budapest, Hungary)	Quantitative: surveys Qualitative: discussion circles, staff evaluation

Table 1. Methodologies chosen by each partner of the H:OUSE project in an intervention territory

particularities of their context and activities. To this end, the combination of quantitative, qualitative and participatory methodologies enabled flexibility according to each context.

Quantitative methodologies were mainly used through surveys and evaluation sheets (Second Tree, Il Sestante and ZRC SAZU). Qualitative methodologies were developed through interviews, individual meetings, focus groups and discussion spaces, as well as informal exchanges during the activities, which allowed feedback to be gathered on the development of the activities and the participants' perspectives (Il Sestante, Refugees Welcome Italia and DORAS). In some cases, feedback was collected through discussions aimed at reflecting on improvements to the activities, potential future collaborations, or through internal evaluations conducted by staff members (Artemisszió). Finally, the partner organisations also highlighted the use of participatory methodologies as group activities, collaborative work, discussion circles and participatory committee meetings, encouraging the active involvement of participants in the reflection and evaluation processes (Il Sestante, Refugees Welcome, Artemisszió and ZRC SAZU).

Figure 3. Training session developed in Padua, Italy

Quantitative data was collected through a shared logbook completed by all project partners (except for Glocal Factory and Iscte). This tool functions as an ongoing monitoring instrument, updated and submitted every six months, and serves as the primary data input for a centralised project database. The database captures key metrics on participants; including their roles, the types of activities conducted, and the nature of interactions within the project, providing a structured overview of implementation progress across territories. Beyond data collection, the logbook contributes to the achievement of the project's objectives by supporting informed adjustments throughout implementation.

This methodological flexibility allowed partners in each territory to adapt data collection to their specific contexts, ensuring respectful and inclusive approaches to capturing the knowledge and experiences of all participants, while drawing on their local expertise. All the information gathered was then compiled and triangulated by the Iscte team responsible for the Impact assessment (Working Package 6), providing a solid basis for assessing the progress, emerging trends, and opportunities for improvement of the H:OUSE project.

3. Participant profiles, engagement and network development

This section highlights participation results, the complementary strategies used across different implementing territories to promote engagement and strengthen networks. It presents the profiles of participants involved during the first phase of the H:OUSE project, analyses the strategies implemented to promote their engagement and active participation, and examines the actions taken to sustain these relationships over time, identifying the key factors contributing to participant retention. Furthermore, it addresses the main challenges encountered throughout these processes.

3.1 Participant profiles and participation overview

The information presented in this section is drawn from the documents “Analysis of Logbook 1” and “Logbook Analysis Report No. 2”, which examine data collected through a logbook tool during the first phase of the H:OUSE project (March 2024 to September 2025).

During this period, 425 individuals participated in project activities. In total, 503 participations were recorded, as some individuals took part in more than one activity.

Figure 5. Number of participants per logbook delivery period

Participants represented 63 different nationalities, including five individuals with dual nationality, reflecting the diversity of the communities reached. In terms of gender, 53% of participants were women and 47% men, with the majority falling within the 20-29 age group.

Of the total participants, 185 had a migrant background, representing nearly half of all participation. Among these, 40 participants represented immigrant or diaspora associations, including 15 asylum and migration NGOs, 14 migrant associations or informal groups, and 11 diaspora communities.

Figure 4. Participants representing a migrant background.

In terms of institutional engagement, 65 participants came from public bodies, with local authorities accounting for the largest share, followed by international organisations, social services, and public schools. Among these, 14 were new institutional partners, most of which were engaged at the local level.

These figures highlight the diversity of actors engaged and provide a basis for analysing the strategies developed to promote participation and strengthen networks across implementing territories.

Figure 6. Profiles of the total 425 participants involved in the H:OUSE activities

3.2 Network development and expansion

Within the framework of the H:OUSE project, the creation and strengthening of networks has been a key focus for driving the development of activities and maximising their impact. The aim has been not only to establish new connections between diverse participants, but also to consolidate existing relationships and foster medium to long-term collaborations.

In the first phase of the H:OUSE project, partners diversified and maintained links with a wide range of stakeholders, including community organisations, diaspora groups, public institutions, private sector actors, volunteers, and local communities.

All partners expanded their networks through the project. Of the 425 participants engaged, 81 were new sponsors collaborating with a partner for the first time (27% of total participations), surpassing the project target of engaging at least 70 sponsors with 20% new participants, representing a variation rate of 186% above the initial objective and before the end of the project. At the same time, 167 participants involved sponsors with prior experience with the partners, indicating that the project also reinforced existing relationships.

Examples from partner organisations illustrate this expansion. Activities facilitated initial contact with new actors, such as associations supporting older people, municipal representatives, and grassroots organisations, while also strengthening ties with migrant and refugee communities. In several cases, engagement led to the activation of new community leaders and the diversification of existing networks.

At least 15 entities have participated in more than three activities under the H:ouse project. This level of engagement is used as an indicator of new networks established around the project, with 15 new networks identified to date.

As an example, activities in Greece by Second Tree enabled initial contact with associations of older people and municipal representatives working in social support for vulnerable groups. For Ireland and DORAS, organisations such as the Clare Local Development Company and the Loughrea Family Resource Centre supported outreach and future activities. For Hungary and the Artemisszió, the involvement of NGOs and grassroots organisations also increased interest in hosting and supporting migrants.

All partners report closer relations with local migrant communities, either by opening new channels or by deepening existing ties. These communities participated actively in project activities, contributing to seminars, information sessions, and local initiatives. For instance, for Artemisszió the project expanded and diversified existing networks, connecting with a wider range of actors within the communities themselves, activating new leaders from the Ukrainian community and bringing representatives from the Venezuelan, Colombian and South African communities into the events.

In DORAS case, groups such as MASI – Movement of Asylum Seekers in Ireland were involved in awareness-raising actions, while newcomers and refugee students took part in local initiatives and discussions in different territories.

Additionally, collaboration with actors such as Clare County Council facilitated coordination and the development of new activities. Public institutions, including universities such as Mary Immaculate College and the University of Limerick, were also involved, with links further developed through collaboration and staff engagement, and additional joint activities foreseen.

Overall, the project contributed not only to creating new connections but also to consolidating relationships and fostering medium- to long-term collaborations across implementing territories.

“Thanks to these combined efforts, the organisation’s network has become broader, more inclusive, and more connected, encompassing institutional actors, organisations, community groups, and volunteers alike. This diverse and engaged network is now a key driver for developing participatory, locally grounded, and sustainable housing solutions.” – Il Sestante, Padova, Italy

3.3 Strategies to promote engagement and participation

Connections were established through multiple channels, including outreach in local contexts, public calls (posted on municipal websites or mailing lists), word of mouth, the renewal of previous connections, and recommendations from other organizations with prior positive experiences. The effectiveness of these channels has depended on a set of facilitating strategies:

Engagement through the promotion of H:OUSE activities

Participation in H:OUSE activities played a central role in establishing and strengthening connections among stakeholders. First, the mapping conducted through WP2 helped identify previously unknown actors, providing a base for further engagement.

Building on this, seminars, trainings, workshops, information sessions, pilot activities, and both formal and informal events offered multiple opportunities for participation. Engagement was further reinforced through targeted initiatives such as self-advocacy training, housing information sessions, and workshops. In particular, WP4 seminars and WP5 pilot activities were frequently highlighted as key enablers for collaboration with new partners, facilitating the organization of awareness-raising events and community initiatives addressing housing challenges.

Moreover, the transnational meeting in Ioannina provided an opportunity to involve local authorities, including council

Figure 7. Participation by the different Working Packages of the project.

members from Limerick, Ireland, and municipality representatives from the 8th district in Budapest, Hungary, further strengthening institutional connections and fostering cross-context collaboration.

- **Locally grounded engagement and language adaptations**

Fieldwork in local contexts, combined with the adaptation of messages to different languages, emerges as a key strategy for breaking down initial barriers and building trust. DORAS and Refugees Welcome Italia underline the importance of locally grounded engagement, rooted in strong community presence and supported by organisational and institutional recognition. Furthermore, outreach efforts with newly arrived refugees in accessible camps, as highlighted by Second Tree, including communication in multiple languages, proved effective in overcoming language obstacles and initial mistrust, thereby facilitating first contact. This is closely linked to approaches that emphasise recognising refugees as individuals, such as Second Tree's "refugees are people" perspective. This more integrated approach has, in cases such as Il Sestante, contributed to building trust, broadening participation and sustaining longer-term engagement. These approaches enabled more inclusive participation and facilitated first contact with diverse groups.

- **Contacting local leaders as a bridge for this engagement**

Direct work with community leaders from diaspora communities strengthened the connections, ensuring that engagement is grounded in local networks. Furthermore, for Il Sestante, it was essential to directly involve community members, particularly through close collaboration with community leaders and local sponsors who acted as bridges for engaging new participants.

- **Word of mouth**

Word of mouth also played a significant role. As Refugees Welcome Italia highlights, when people feel welcome, supported, and integrated into activities, they are more likely to involve new stakeholders. Positive experiences of participation encouraged participants to invite others, creating a snowball effect and expanding the reach of activities.

- **Co-designing activities, tools and methodologies from the beginning**

Involving participants in the design of activities, tools, and methodologies strengthened their sense of ownership and ensured that actions were better adapted to local needs. As Il Sestante points out, rather than simply participating in predefined initiatives, community members, beneficiaries and other stakeholders have contributed with ideas, shaped activities and proposed approaches suited to their needs. This reinforces motivation and a sense of belonging to the project, and promotes responses that are more closely connected to local realities and fosters a sense of commitment that ensures continuity.

- **Diversity of the network**

The presence of participants with different experiences encouraged engagement from other stakeholders, as interacting with people unlike themselves fostered broader participation. For Il Sestante, the H:OUSE project opened a new dialogue with the Padua City Council's Commission for Foreign Citizens, bringing together representatives from Albania, Sri Lanka, India, Nigeria, Pakistan, Ivory Coast, Philippines, Moldova, Morocco, Iran, and China. At the same time, bonds were strengthened with the Nigerian, Albanian, Bangladeshi, Ukrainian, Pakistani, and Gambian communities.

Refugees Welcome Italia experienced a similar effect, as collaboration with two diaspora communities involved in the Ravenna co-housing pilot project, the Centre for Islamic Studies (Moschea della Pace) and the Bangladeshi community of the Via Bosi Maramotti mosque, became more solid and sustained. At DORAS, cooperation with local authorities generated positive feedback and a clear willingness to continue the work, further reinforcing engagement and demonstrating how diversity among participants can attract new stakeholders and strengthen networks.

“Housing is not only a concern for those working in reception services. Many other actors can and should care about migrants’ access to housing.” -Reception centre worker, Ravenna, Italy

3.4 Enabling factors for institutional engagement

Despite differences in local context, partners identified a consistent set of conditions that facilitated effective collaboration with public institutions, recognized as both challenging and crucial:

- **Pre-existing trust relationships**

Partners emphasise that for engaging institutional entities the role of prior groundwork was crucial. This includes the partners’ long-standing presence and consistent involvement in their territories, a point particularly emphasised by Second Tree, as well as by Il Sestante, Refugees Welcome Italia and DORAS. This way, pre-existing relationships of trust and continuity have been essential in enabling effective engagement with institutions and enabling new ways of collaboration.

- **Early and sustained involvement**

Equally important was the strategy of early and close involvement, which ensured that institutional stakeholders were engaged from the very beginning. Through introductory meetings, local seminars, participatory sessions, and ongoing exchanges, these stakeholders were able to contribute actively and provide feedback. This continuous interaction not only helped align expectations and strengthen mutual understanding but also ensured that project activities remained coherent with local policies and priorities.

- **The urgency of the housing crisis**

The critical issue of housing and migrants' limited access to it underscores the importance of the topic across different territories. This urgency has served as a crucial facilitator, prompting institutions to engage actively. Within this context, H:OUSE emerges as a space of opportunity for the public sector, offering a platform for meaningful involvement and intervention, as highlighted by Il Sestante and DORAS.

- **Invitations to events and international meetings**

Inviting local administrators to events and international meetings proved to be a key engagement strategy. This included linking them to public events, targeted meetings, and providing continuous updates on project progress. For Il Sestante, these approaches were decisive in attracting the Municipal Councillor for Housing Policies, the Housing Office of the Municipality of Padua, and the Municipal Commission for Foreign Residents.

Another important facilitator was the invitation of local administrators to the international meeting in Ioannina. This event enabled partners such as ZRC SAZU and Artemisszió to strengthen engagement and build closer relationships with these institutional actors.

- **Initial contact through a single department**

Initial contact with a single public department helped raise awareness of the H:OUSE project across other municipal sections, in the case of Refugees Welcome.

3.5 Sustaining participant engagement

Maintaining participant engagement over time emerged as a key priority. It was identified as essential not only for the implementation of project activities, but also for building a supportive and engaged community around the initiatives, fostering trust and shared learning. In this context, continuous participation has been a key factor in strengthening relationships and enabling long-term collaboration.

For example, at ZRC SAZU, this continuity translated into closer links with migrant-led associations such as Afriška vas (African village), Društvo Medkulturni dialog (Association Intercultural dialogue), Zavod Dress for Success (Association Dress for Success). These groups first joined local participatory committees and later became service providers in the housing pilot actions. Similarly, Second Tree highlighted the importance of continuity, noting the sustained involvement of refugees, including newcomers and students, as motivated participants to continue in the project.

To maintain the networks created, the following strategies were implemented throughout the first phase of the H:OUSE project:

- **Unity and a shared purpose from the beginning**

The network itself has proven to be a key factor. At ZRC SAZU, it helped support sponsors' willingness to engage in pilot activities. Similarly, Refugees Welcome Italia highlights that, from the very beginning, the network fostered a sense of unity and a shared purpose. DORAS also underlines the importance of established partners, such as the Mary Immaculate College CS group and Limerick County, in maintaining consistent engagement. At Artemisszió, individual sponsors, particularly those contributing the most volunteers and diaspora leaders, have even become regular members, creating continuity from within.

"We need to keep talking about housing and make sure it remains on the political agenda, not only in connection with projects like H:OUSE, which will eventually come to an end." - Shelter coordinator Ravenna, Italy

- **Practical support linked to real needs and flexible tools**

Sustaining participation over time proved to be both a strategic priority and a practical challenge. Partners found that structured instruments, such as written agreements, internal regulations, and shared operational frameworks, were valuable in clarifying roles and responsibilities, and in providing a stable foundation for pilot activities.

At the same time, these formal tools alone were not sufficient to ensure continued engagement. Many participants, including community leaders and volunteers, hold their roles on a voluntary basis, balancing them alongside professional and personal commitments, which made consistent attendance difficult. In Ravenna, Refugees Welcome Italia observed that participation among newcomers was often variable, with many unable to attend every session due to shift work. Il Sestante similarly highlighted that flexibility is essential, without it, participation narrows to those with the most availability, which risks undermining the diversity and representativeness of the community being built.

In response, partners across territories combined flexible scheduling, online formats, and ongoing day-to-day dialogue with participants to adapt activities to their real circumstances. This approach reflected a broader understanding that genuine community participation cannot be imposed through fixed structures alone but must be continuously negotiated and supported.

- **Regular contact and follow-up with participants, ensuring continuity, shared learning and long-term collaboration.**

ZRC SAZU stresses that maintaining regular contact with network members, whether by email, telephone or in person, ensures the continuity of activities and the implementation of commitments.

- **Scale of the territory**

By the time of the mid-term report, several partners had achieved a stable level of engagement. ZRC SAZU, for example, highlights that the relatively small size of its territory

facilitates this process, as fewer entities are involved in working with migrants and refugees, making it easier to maintain strong connections. In this context, strengthening the network has been crucial for sustaining participation.

3.6 Challenges in network development and participation

Despite positive results, partners identified several challenges affecting network creation and sustainability. It is useful to distinguish between two types of constraints encountered in network creation. Internal project limitations, such as challenges in local engagement, time pressures, scheduling conflicts, and limited volunteer availability, can be addressed through flexible planning and adapted tools. In contrast, structural or external constraints, including hostile political environments, underfunded public housing systems, and the marginalisation of NGOs in certain national contexts, require responses that go beyond project-level intervention and point to the need for systemic policy change.

- **Trust and local engagement**

The first challenge was ensuring that the different voices within each community genuinely had space to be heard. Addressing this required a flexible and inclusive approach, capable of accommodating internal differences and lowering barriers to participation.

As an example, Second Tree notes that mistrust from parts of local society has complicated the involvement of local stakeholders. To address this, the organisation has relied on expanding existing local networks, involving students, and strengthening collaboration with the municipality. Similarly, Il Sestante highlights difficulties in engaging actors already active in housing, as well as community leaders and volunteers with limited time. To overcome these barriers, the organisation emphasises offering practical support linked to real needs, and using flexible participation tools, including formal and informal meetings, virtual options, and co-design spaces, to maintain engagement and trust.

- **Private sector involvement**

Refugees Welcome Italia identifies the main difficulty as engaging the private sector, including banks, real estate agencies, and property owners. Given the fragmented nature of this sector, individualised contacts are required, and response rates have been low. One potential solution is greater institutional involvement through formal public calls for proposals, which would provide legitimacy and visibility; however, a lack of political commitment currently limits this option.

- **Institutional and coordination challenges**

Il Sestante notes that conflicts and differing institutional agendas sometimes limited participation. Maintaining consistent engagement therefore requires flexibility, continuous dialogue, and ongoing updates on project developments. ZRC SAZU further highlights that the workload of state employees, often overburdened, reduces their capacity to take on additional initiatives in cooperation with NGOs. For Refugees Welcome Italia, constraints arose from the lack of inter-departmental coordination.

- **Political and structural constraints**

In Hungary, NGOs working on migration face a hostile environment, with state actors often criminalising organisations active in this field. Engagement is thus restricted to municipalities, and even then, primarily those led by opposition parties. On a more structural level, also Artemisszió emphasises that scarcity of resources and government policies make it difficult to create sustainable networks, although direct support for migrants, such as funding for renovations or rent, can help alleviate these limitations. Although this exceeds the H:OUSE project’s scope, direct funding, such as for renovations or rent subsidies, is proposed as a potential support measure.

Figure 8 Training session in Ljubljana, Slovenia

“Everything is very positive, but it seems that we are mostly engaging with the same group of professionals. The dialogue with migrants is important as well, but where are the real estate agencies?”
- Facilitator representative of Refugees Welcome Italia, Ravenna, Italy

4. Knowledge sharing

Across all partner territories, knowledge sharing emerged as one of the most crucial dimensions of the H:OUSE project, not only as a vehicle for transmitting information, but as a process through which participants collectively constructed new frameworks for understanding housing as a structural and collective issue. This section examines how that process unfolded; the activities that enabled it, the importance of the shared spaces that sustained it and the limitations that constrained it.

4.1 Activities and their contribution to understanding migrants' experiences

Activities aimed at addressing the challenge of access to housing have helped deepen understanding in different ways, from capacity building and advocacy to participation and co-design, as well as awareness-raising and dissemination.

- **Capacity building and advocacy**

Throughout the first stage of the H:OUSE project, the partners organised activities that helped participants better understand housing rights and accessibility issues, while also creating opportunities for direct engagement with sponsors and fostering a deeper understanding of their experiences and challenges.

“The information provided through our training was new to them and that they are willing and motivated to stay in our network and support further.” -Local student, Ioannina, Greece

Second Tree carried out various activities aimed at capacity building, such as training in administrative self-advocacy and housing information sessions for refugees, as well as training for local sponsors interested in supporting newcomers.

Il Sestante, in turn, organised four local seminars and three training sessions, as well as introducing participatory co-design and planning sessions. The seminars sought to involve landlords and sponsors in the field of housing issues and solutions, together with the definition of future community activities. The training sessions aimed at sponsors, community leaders and migrant representatives reinforced advocacy skills, intercultural understanding and participatory approaches. The co-design and planning processes adapted pilot activities to local needs, identified housing and language support requirements, and facilitated the involvement of operators and volunteers. These actions strengthened understanding of the daily challenges faced by refugees and promoted empowerment and collaboration between communities, sponsors and local actors.

Refugees Welcome Italia focused its training programme on experience-based learning through case studies, role-playing and interactive discussions, fostering empathy and the adoption of a refugee-centred perspective.

ZRC SAZU developed three pilot projects, including an info-point service, a conversation club and training in intercultural mediation, highlighting the importance of creating safe and supportive spaces for exchange.

DORAS promoted local seminars and training for sponsors, connecting diaspora leaders and volunteers, improving understanding of the challenges related to housing and integration.

Artemisszió also trained volunteers, involved beneficiaries and strengthened institutional partnerships through local and international events.

- **Participation and co-design**

Il Sestante and Artemisszió conducted co-design workshops and participatory meetings to adapt pilot activities to local contexts. These processes ensured that activities responded to participants' real needs, promoted shared ownership, and strengthened collaboration between institutional partners and communities.

- **Awareness raising and dissemination**

Seminars and dissemination events were held, such as those organised by Il Sestante, Refugees Welcome Italia and DORAS, as well as communication and promotion activities involving NGOs and local organisations. These actions increased understanding of the challenges faced by refugees, promoted the active participation of local actors and raised awareness of good practices and the Community Sponsorship approach.

4.2 Fostering dialogue through shared spaces

Creating shared spaces for exchange has proven essential in fostering dialogue and helping participants feel welcome, regardless of their specific profile. In practice, partners have implemented these spaces, adapting them to local contexts and needs.

“One of the most significant added values of the project was not only the creation of new relationships, but also the establishment of a shared space for dialogue and exchange. This space allowed stakeholders to collectively reflect on migration-related challenges, explore innovative strategies and adopt more systemic approaches, moving beyond fragmented and individualised interventions.” Member of the staff of Refugees Welcome Italia, Ravenna, Italy

“Exchanges between the different organizations are very useful. We should institutionalize this. We could take turns organizing these. The presence of the target group is particularly valuable” Participant, Budapest, Hungary

“It is important to create spaces for meeting and exchange among organizations working on these issues; creating a manifesto could be a functional tool to guide a network for awareness-raising and for the exchange of internal skills and expertise.” Staff from local organization, Padua, Italy

- **Activities to promote dialogue and reflection**

These spaces have fostered moments of shared learning, joint reflection, and networking, providing opportunities for dialogue, collaboration, and knowledge exchange. Discussion groups in local seminars and participatory sessions organised by Il Sestante allowed participants to collectively analyse challenges and share perspectives, offering structured settings for dialogue that can be extended throughout pilot actions. Even though many actors were already familiar with each other and active in the migration field, these sessions allowed participants to deepen relationships, build trust, and open new possibilities for collaboration and knowledge transfer, including exchanges between sponsors and between sponsors and beneficiaries.

- **Training and mentoring activities**

Training and mentoring activities facilitated exchanges both among sponsors and between sponsors and beneficiaries. Volunteer training, language teachers and mentors, follow-up sessions, case discussions, and mentor-mentee programmes implemented by Artemisszió strengthened relationships and supported knowledge transfer. Training sessions and workshops organised by Refugees Welcome Italia, incorporating case studies, role-playing, and interactive discussions, encouraged a refugee-centred perspective and intercultural understanding, while also supporting the involvement of new sponsors and volunteers.

“These break moments are perfect opportunities to get to know each other better and to exchange ideas and perspectives” - Leader of the local Nigerian community, Ravenna, Italy

- **Cultural events and informal spaces**

Furthermore, informal settings played a key role in fostering dialogue and interaction, including meals, coffee breaks, intercultural activities, as well as festivals and cultural events. These spaces provided opportunities for networking and knowledge exchange at the same level, despite the diversity of actors involved, reinforcing community building. Examples of such events include a New Year’s cultural gathering organised by Second Tree, which brought together refugees and members of the local community; conversation clubs and informal meetings for migrants and refugees developed by ZRC SAZU, networking activities implemented by Artemisszió during local and international events, and the Festival of Proximity led by Il Sestante, which offered additional opportunities for participants to share experiences, build trust, and strengthen connections within the network.

“What an amazing experience! It was my first event at Mira Haz, and I am so happy that I chose this cultural evening. The organizers did a beautiful job introducing us to this beautiful country. The interactive games were so much fun, and getting to take home an 'oleh-oleh' (souvenir) was such a thoughtful surprise. The coffee and snacks were delicious too. It's definitely one of the most vibrant events I've attended here so far!” - Participant of a intercultural activity, Budapest, Hungary

- **Dialogue spaces and institutional platforms**

Dedicated dialogue areas and municipal platforms for communication offered structured opportunities for intersectoral collaboration on migrant housing. Refugees Welcome Italia created specific dialogue areas that enabled future collaboration with local administration, while ZRC SAZU worked with the municipality to provide participatory tools, such as the participatory committee in Škofja Loka, involving employees from state institutions, schools, and NGOs. DORAS also facilitated direct exchanges between local actors during a local seminar in Limerick, where representatives from Limerick City Council met a member of MASI (Movement of Asylum Seekers in Ireland), allowing a constructive confrontation between institutional perspectives and migrant experiences. These spaces encouraged mutual recognition as partners, fostered collaboration, and enabled significant knowledge transfer, creating a clearly defined and recognised framework for exchange that can continue to support pilot actions in the future.

However, knowledge exchanges between different sponsors have not occurred uniformly across all implementation territories. Part of the explanation lies in the fact that some initiatives were still in a consolidation phase at the time of gathering data for the creation of the present mid-term report. Besides the fact that exchanges, while strengthening trust and relationships, have not always resulted in concrete operational outcomes. Despite these limitations, several partners report that the project has created a clearly defined and recognised space for exchange. The H:OUSE project allowed actors to deepen existing relationships, get to know each other better within the network, and open up new possibilities for collaboration and knowledge transfer. Refugees Welcome Italia highlighted that the multi-stakeholder format fostered mutual learning and a more comprehensive understanding of local housing challenges. Overall, these exchange spaces have contributed to stronger networks, increased dialogue, and enhanced capacity among participants, sponsors, and local actors.

“H:OUSE is part of the broader strategic framework of the City of Ravenna, which brings together multiple initiatives and projects with the aim of integrating them into a coherent system in order to strengthen and expand integration services” - Administrative Manager of the Migration Policies Office , Ravenna, Italy

4.3 Improved understanding of housing issues and their drivers among local actors

The activities contributed to broadening understanding of effective tools and strategies for sponsors, particularly by shifting from individual, reactive approaches to collaborative, network-based practices.

- **Strengthening of practical knowledge**

Partners reported improvements in practical understanding of housing processes and strategies. Migrants gained knowledge about housing rights, rental procedures, and administrative processes, alongside new ways to approach housing challenges. Sponsors and volunteers improved their capacity to address these challenges, supported by the exchange of experiences and good practices. Il Sestante highlighted the consolidation of knowledge among experienced actors, while Refugees Welcome Italia noted that new actors, including volunteers and union representatives, expanded their understanding.

- **Recognition of vulnerabilities and discrimination**

The activities increased awareness of the specific barriers faced by migrants. Second Tree observed greater understanding among local actors of migrants' vulnerability in accessing housing. ZRC SAZU reported discussions on discriminatory rental practices, informal contracts, exploitation, and poor living conditions, helping sponsors recognise structural inequities and act more sensitively.

- **Ensuring beneficiaries shift from a consultative role to becoming active participants.**

At Refugees Welcome Italia, a decisive step was to ensure that communities moved from playing an advisory role to becoming active partners.

- **Relational and network-based learning**

Participatory activities promoted reflection, comparison of approaches, sharing of difficulties, and co-design of solutions, as reflected by DORAS. Artemisszió emphasised the creation of ties between migrants and the local population, even if centralised support remained a challenge. Il Sestante noted that safe spaces for exchange reinforced network-based approaches and highlighted the importance of mutual support and coordinated community responses. Refugees Welcome Italia provided newly engaged sponsors with access to innovative strategies, relational tools, and approaches centred on empowering migrants' autonomy, encouraging reflective and emotional learning, and promoting continuous improvement.

“Hearing how others handled similar cases made me feel less alone and more confident in supporting newcomers.” - Community sponsor, Padua, Italy

- **Housing crisis as a structural challenge**

One of the most significant changes documented through the knowledge-sharing process was behavioural. The participants moved from viewing housing difficulties as individual issues to recognising them as structural conditions rooted in broader urban and political dynamics. The H:OUSE project highlighted that the barriers faced by migrants, such as linguistic, cultural, administrative and economic constraints, do not exist in isolation, but as an additional layer of complexity within a housing crisis affecting the migrant community. Among sponsors and local participants, this rethinking translated into a greater practical capacity, a stronger sense of shared responsibility, and a growing conviction that coordinated and collective responses are necessary.

“The impact of this network and of the new connections on the project was highly significant, as it enabled the inclusion of multiple perspectives and facilitated a collective approach to issues that are strongly felt within the local community, fostering shared responsibility and reducing the burden on individual actors.” - Member of the staff of Refugees Welcome Italia, Ravenna, Italy

Figure 9. Training developed in Ravenna, Italy

“These sessions opened my eyes to how housing is a shared responsibility and not just an individual problem.” - Participant, Padua, Italy

Figure 10. Pilot activity developed in Padua, Italy

“It is a cultural, political and administrative issue. It is necessary to address it from multiple perspectives.” - Member of La Nuova Stella Polare, Padua, Italy

“For systemic challenges, systemic solutions are needed. No one can address them alone.” - Member of the Ravenna Municipality staff, Ravenna, Italy

4. 4 Shifting towards greater engagement and collective commitment

Although many partners already had prior interest in migrants' housing, the activities reinforced and broadened this concern, particularly by highlighting the structural nature of housing challenges, as noted by Il Sestante and Refugees Welcome Italia. For new participants, students, institutional representatives, and private-sector partners, the activities introduced them to the central role of housing in effective integration (Second Tree, Il Sestante, Refugees Welcome Italia).

- **Active engagement**

Refugees Welcome Italia observed that participants demonstrated commitment by attending sessions outside regular hours and remaining actively involved despite fatigue, showing the relevance and perceived value of the project. ZRC SAZU noted that sponsors, service providers, and community members engaged more actively in sharing information, asking questions, and exploring practical solutions during the activities. DORAS highlighted the inclusion of new profiles, such as accommodation providers, in the conversation, further broadening perspectives.

- **Practical learning and support**

Artemisszió reported that cooperation with the 8th District Municipality raised awareness of housing challenges. Even though plans for expanded social housing were paused, volunteers and mentors now receive training on practical aspects of housing, legal procedures, contracts, landlord-tenant relations, and conflict management, and actively support migrants. Local partner organisations also gained further attention to housing through shared research and collective reflection.

“Without this support, I would have given up. Now I understand my rights and where to ask for help.” - Participant, Padua, Italy

- **Collective commitment and social cohesion/outcomes**

Beyond individual change, several partners documented a shift toward collective commitment. Il Sestante reported that participants recognised the need to work collectively within the territory to counter stereotypes and promote inclusive conditions, leading to the co-development of a community manifesto on anti-racist approaches to housing (Anti-Racist Manifesto for Padua). Refugees Welcome Italia noted that the multi-stakeholder format itself became a driver of mutual accountability. The participants who understood housing as a shared structural problem were more likely to sustain engagement beyond individual sessions and to take initiative within their own networks.

This collective dimension, the emergence of a shared narrative and a disposition toward coordinated action, is arguably the most durable output of the knowledge-sharing process, and the one most likely to outlast the project's duration.

“I was not aware of the extent of the initiatives already underway in this field. Our community is also working to identify housing solutions, and we strongly welcome the opportunity to collaborate within this project framework” - Representative of the Islamic community of the Moschea della Pace in Ravenna, Ravenna, Italy

4. 5 Challenges in communicating and accessing knowledge

- **Language and knowledge barriers**

Differences in language and varying levels of prior experience among participants affected communication. Il Sestante reported that these factors made it difficult to share knowledge consistently. Practical exercises such as role-plays, group discussions, and participatory methods helped overcome these challenges. Second Tree also highlighted that mistrust from locals toward humanitarian NGOs and differing daily priorities created additional obstacles.

- **Structural and external constraints**

External factors beyond the scope of the project limited knowledge generation. Refugees Welcome Italia noted that the absence of comprehensive, publicly accessible information on vacant or potentially recoverable housing, especially in the private sector, was a major barrier. Collaboration with AUSER, the public housing management body in Ravenna, partially addressed this issue, but gaps in private housing data remained. Artemisszió emphasised that while internal communication within their sensitised network was smooth, reaching the broader local population, those with limited interest or information on migration, was challenging. Limited access to central government channels also reduced advocacy capacity.

- **Separation of the different participant profiles**

Separating training groups by profile (sponsors and newcomers working in parallel rather than together) was another factor that, as Refugees Welcome Italia observed, limited the depth of direct exchange during the initial phase, an approach worth reconsidering in the second phase.

3.6 Tools and instruments to improve knowledge sharing

Increased outreach and visibility.

Second Tree highlighted the need for greater outreach and visibility within the local community to engage more people. Artemisszió also emphasised the importance of extending their reach, through intercultural festivals and culinary programmes, while noting the difficulty of engaging with central government actors.

- **Improving knowledge-sharing tools and formats**

Il Sestante proposed developing guides in different languages, visual aids, case-study toolkits and step-by-step materials to support understanding and knowledge sharing. Furthermore they suggest tailored sessions for different target groups (sponsors, community leaders, landlords, local actors) and the use of interactive tools such as role-play, simulations, and online platforms to strengthen practical learning and exchange. Refugees Welcome Italia also reported that jointly mapping housing search steps and local services with newcomers strengthened access to information and produced structured materials usable in practice.

“Seeing examples from other cases made me realize that the housing challenges are systemic, not just personal” - Participant, Padua, Italy

- **Strengthening evidence-based planning and institutional dialogue**

Refugees Welcome Italia identified limited access to publicly available data as a key constraint and suggested structured dialogue with local institutions to secure funding for research and mapping of vacant housing stock, in order to support evidence-based decision-making.

- **Raising awareness of housing access barriers**

DORAS underlined that improving awareness of actual housing access issues would further strengthen the impact of the activities

- **Interactive and peer-based learning**

Second Tree highlighted regular self-advocacy trainings, practical housing information sessions, and cultural events as effective formats for continuous feedback and informal knowledge exchange. Il Sestante emphasised interactive methods (role-plays, case studies, group discussions), peer-to-peer exchange between experienced sponsors and newcomers, and informal follow-up discussions that fostered trust and collaborative problem-solving. Refugees Welcome Italia also reported open sharing of practices and continued exchanges beyond sessions, describing the creation of a shared knowledge space as a key added value.

“I am happy that the program was practical. It is difficult to speak about severe cases and about the possibilities we have. Despite the difficulties, we tried to find solutions.” - Participant in multistakeholder planning, Budapest, Hungary

- **Inclusive environments and common language as enabling factors.**

Il Sestante noted that accessible community-based venues and mixed participant composition enriched dialogue. ZRC SAZU underlined that a common linguistic base (Ukrainian and Russian) enabled fluent communication, trust-building, and active participation.

“It helped me understand how to talk to landlords and avoid misunderstandings with newcomers.” - Community sponsor , Padua, Italy

Figure 11. Pilot activity developed in Ravenna, Italy

"Especially for people who have arrived recently, it would be important to create dedicated spaces and training courses, particularly on legal procedures. For those going through a housing pathway, specific courses on orientation to public services and bureaucracy would also be essential. Informal support alone is not sufficient" - Community sponsor, Padua, Italy

Figure 12. Training developed in Budapest, Hungary

“During the role play, I found myself reliving a situation I had already experienced, and it made me feel understood and heard.” - Participant, Ravenna, Italy

5. Housing solutions

Throughout the first stage of the H:OUSE project, partners generated a range of insights into the barriers refugees face in accessing housing, as well as strategies to overcome them. These insights are based on direct engagement with refugees, community sponsors, landlords, and local stakeholders through participatory workshops, training sessions, and multi-stakeholder dialogues.

5.1 Improving housing access: insights from practice

- **Multifaceted nature of housing barriers**

A key insight is the complexity of housing barriers, which are linguistic, cultural, administrative, economic, and social in nature, and require coordinated, context-specific responses. Partners noted that in highly competitive rental contexts without a centralised social housing system, access becomes particularly difficult for newcomers, and that the severity of the housing crisis often outweighs the available solutions.

- **Integration as a pathway to housing**

Several partners highlighted that improving integration, through access to employment, language learning, and contact with the local community, is one of the most effective ways to facilitate access to housing. Community sponsorship from the outset improves knowledge of the local environment and increases the chances of entering the rental market. In this context, self-advocacy and knowledge sharing were identified as crucial tools for refugees navigating the housing system.

- **Collaboration and dismantling discrimination**

Overcoming housing barriers demands collaboration between local authorities, civil society, and migrant communities. Interactive workshops and meetings with property owners and community sponsors revealed the need to actively dismantle racist stereotypes, prompting the development of pilot activities alongside an anti-racist

manifesto for community life. Partners also emphasised that well-informed mentors, cooperation with other professionals, and understanding the legal framework are essential when cases exceed individual competencies.

“Migrant integration is still underestimated and underappreciated while it is crucial for migrants to become independent in the new host society. We need more tools and strategies to figure out how to further develop and create a more welcoming, more inclusive and enabling environment for new people arriving to host societies.” - Participant, Maribor , ZRC SAZU

- **Economic and structural factors**

Economic guarantees were identified as a crucial factor for accessing housing. While the project cannot intervene directly, local initiatives such as “Padova per Abitanci” provide legal and financial support to tenants and landlords, fostering trust and inclusive housing models, piloting the reuse of vacant properties, and strengthening community networks. These examples demonstrate how coordinated, place-based services can facilitate access to housing for vulnerable groups.

“I believe that housing is the main challenge here in Ravenna. Without a stable home, I have nothing that truly ties me to the city. Even after completing my integration pathway here, I am still forced to leave.” Participant, Ravenna, Italy

- **Rethinking housing models**

Several partners highlighted the need to move beyond traditional individual-focused rental approaches. Refugees Welcome Italia proposed addressing complementary needs together, for instance by connecting experiences of loneliness among older people and migrants, experimenting with co-housing models, and promoting shared solutions that strengthen social inclusion.

- **Policy-level implications**

From a policy perspective, dedicated housing services or help desks are needed so that migrants do not rely exclusively on the private rental market. Coordinated public services, supported by community actors, are key to ensuring equitable access to housing.

- **Strengthening networks and collaboration**

One of the most common strategies focused on the importance of networks and collaboration. Strengthening community sponsorship networks and encouraging local actors, volunteers, and organisations to coordinate and share responsibilities creates a safety net for newcomers and reduces isolation, as observed by Il Sestante. Refugees Welcome Italia proposed a permanent multi-stakeholder housing working group to ensure continuity, institutional memory, and long-term impact. Second Tree emphasised collaboration with municipal authorities to increase outreach and visibility in local society.

Local governance is a crucial aspect in this regard, improving coordination between public institutions and civil society, increasing the political visibility of housing as a priority, and creating more sustainable support mechanisms for refugees and vulnerable groups. Engaging students, community members, and municipal authorities also helped create informal support systems and expand housing opportunities, according to Second Tree. Coordinated work among organisations and NGOs at the national level can further strengthen instruments such as Community Sponsorship and other Humanitarian Pathways, facilitating newcomers’ access to housing solutions, as highlighted by DORAS.

This was a great experience. Meetings with my mentor helped me feel more confident in

a new country. It wasn't just about information, but about real friendship. We cooked together, visited museums and even introduced our families to each other. We still keep in touch and I'm very grateful for such a warm welcome to Hungary. (Participant in an activity organised by Artemisszio)

- **Integration, awareness-raising, and capacity building**

Integration and raising awareness were key strategies for improving access to housing. Il Sestante observed that strengthening local understanding of housing as a systemic issue promotes inclusive policies and initiatives, enhances practical skills among sponsors, and empowers refugees to seek housing independently. DORAS emphasised the role of local community support and experience sharing, which enabled newcomers to actively participate in community life.

ZRC SAZU developed language and conversation clubs focused on housing-related skills, such as communicating with landlords, understanding advertisements, and completing administrative paperwork, helping migrants become more self-sufficient. Il Sestante also implemented Italian language courses focused on housing, work, and daily life to reduce language and cultural barriers. Training sessions and seminars allowed both experienced and new sponsors to consolidate knowledge and discover new tools for supporting housing access. Cultural and community events facilitated interaction between refugees and local residents, reducing social distance and fostering trust and mutual understanding, as noted by Second Tree.

- **Practical support and empowerment**

Practical and empowerment-oriented activities played a key role in enabling refugees to navigate the housing system. Role-plays, case studies, and interactive workshops allowed participants to explore real-life housing challenges and develop concrete strategies.

- **Innovative service models and information tools**

ZRC SAZU highlighted the creation of an information point providing cultural mediation, translation support, and direct assistance with apartment searches, which increased housing opportunities during the pilot phase. Refugees Welcome Italia reported the successful development of innovative ideas, such as co-housing models, bringing together people from different professional backgrounds around a shared vision. These approaches proved effective in fostering mutual understanding and collective ownership of housing challenges.

5.2 Key challenges in accessing housing solutions

Most partners identified significant difficulties in finding housing solutions, noting that the scale of the problem exceeds the project's capacity for systemic intervention. These challenges can be grouped into the following categories:

- **Structural and systemic barriers**

The housing crisis is deeply rooted, and the limited scope of project-based interventions cannot generate sustainable, long-term solutions without strong public policy support. Il Sestante highlighted limited housing stock, long waiting lists, high rents, and unsuitable conditions. Refugees Welcome Italia stressed the difficulty of designing structured, long-term solutions beyond temporary or emergency-based approaches, emphasising the need for inclusive, rights-based access to housing that ensures autonomy and long-term stability. Artemisszió underlined that structural problems require structural solutions, including increased social housing, a more regulated rental market, targeted financial support for newcomers (especially refugees), robust integration strategies such as free or affordable language courses, and the removal of anti-migration rhetoric. Only with these structural conditions in place can communities complement existing systems and contribute effectively to state-led integration strategies.

DORAS noted that the housing crisis in Ireland affects the entire population, which limits the potential for innovative, transversal solutions at the local level. Overall, the systemic nature of the crisis means that housing barriers are shared by both newcomers and the wider community.

- **Limited public involvement and uneven distribution of responsibility**

Partners emphasised that as long as housing is not addressed comprehensively by public authorities, sustainable solutions remain difficult. Refugees Welcome Italia reported that the burden often falls on local actors with limited resources and restricted institutional support. Discussions highlighted the need to broaden responsibility beyond reception and integration services, fostering shared ownership of housing challenges across institutional and social actors.

- **Constraints of the private rental market**

Accessing housing through the private rental sector proved challenging. Il Sestante noted high rents, scarce affordable units, and unsuitable living conditions. Artemisszió reported that, since the project could not provide direct financial contributions and cooperation with the central government was limited, they had to focus on the private rental market, encountering multiple constraints. ZRC SAZU observed that landlords often exercise strong discretion when selecting tenants and may be reluctant to rent to foreigners without trusted connections.

- **Social, cultural, and administrative barriers**

Language barriers, limited knowledge of procedures (Second Tree), discrimination, reluctance from landlords, and complex administrative requirements (Il Sestante) were consistently mentioned. High mobility among refugees and mistrust from some local communities further complicated access. These factors underline that cultural, social, and

procedural dimensions significantly shape housing opportunities.

- **Limited resources and fragmented support networks**

Partners stressed that responsibility for finding housing solutions often falls on a small number of actors with limited resources. Second Tree and Refugees Welcome Italia noted that restricted sponsor networks reduce the number of available options. Il Sestante highlighted fragmented communication and coordination among stakeholders, limiting the sharing of potential solutions and good practices.

- **Communication and knowledge constraints**

Disseminating information about housing solutions among refugees and local actors remains difficult. Second Tree observed that cultural and language differences can hinder newcomers' ability to communicate needs. Il Sestante noted that implicit biases may make engagement with landlords sensitive, while limited awareness of procedures and housing rights further complicates navigation of official systems.

5.3 Potential tools or instruments to address housing challenges

- **Bottom-up mobilisation and collective advocacy**

As highlighted by Refugees Welcome Italia, one key proposal was the development of a bottom-up movement capable of bringing housing issues higher onto the public and political agenda. Participants stressed the importance of collective mobilisation and coordinated advocacy to ensure that housing is no longer treated as a marginal or purely technical matter, but as a central social and political priority. The combined use of grassroots action and media engagement — including storytelling, data-driven narratives, and public campaigns — was seen as a powerful lever to influence public discourse, strengthen institutional accountability, and push for structural housing reforms.

- **Coordination networks and exchange mechanisms**

Several partners emphasised the need to strengthen coordination among stakeholders. Il Sestante proposed regular meetings or digital forums bringing together sponsors, local authorities, and NGOs to share best practices, discuss ongoing cases, and collectively identify solutions. In the same spirit, Artemisszió underlined that the exchange of methodologies within the partnership is essential to mutual learning and inspiration.

Building on this, one of the strongest needs to emerge at the local level, through the experience of Refugees Welcome Italia, was the creation of a structured and permanent space where housing-related information could be collected, shared, and accessed by all relevant stakeholders. This would function as a dedicated "housing help desk" or one-stop shop, serving as a central reference point for information, services, and coordination. Examples of similar initiatives already exist in neighbouring municipalities that have

moved in this direction, suggesting that the model is both viable and replicable.

However, fully implementing such a structure proved beyond the reach of the current project timeframe. Engaging the local housing policy office, a key institutional actor for this kind of initiative, was not possible during project implementation, leaving this ambition partially unfulfilled.

Faced with this constraint, the network established through the project has nonetheless sought a path forward. While a public-facing service could not be launched, the partnerships and working relationships built over the course of the project will continue to serve as an internal coordination and knowledge-sharing mechanism among partners and local stakeholders. This approach, though more modest in scope, aims to sustain collaboration beyond the project's formal duration, and to keep alive the longer-term aspiration of a more structured, institutionally anchored housing support system.

- **Centralised information and practical guidance tools**

Second Tree suggested the creation of a centralised information and guidance platform, online or offline, and available in multiple languages. Complementarily, Il Sestante proposed practical guides and glossaries explaining local rental procedures, tenant rights, and cultural expectations, enabling migrants to navigate administrative processes more confidently.

- **Communication, outreach and mediation tools**

Targeted outreach campaigns to raise awareness among local communities about refugee needs and project objectives were proposed by Second Tree. In addition, Il Sestante recommended structured communication and mediation tools — including templates, training sessions, role-play scenarios, and case studies — to support dialogue between newcomers and landlords.

- **Sponsor databases and structured housing offers**

Second Tree proposed the creation of a local sponsor database and coordination tool to track potential sponsors, available housing, and support services. Along similar lines, DORAS suggested structured programmes specifically engaging landlords, facilitating concrete housing offers for migrants.

- **Monitoring, feedback and local support services**

Simple evaluation and feedback forms were proposed to allow migrants and sponsors to report challenges and successes, helping to identify recurring obstacles and improve future interventions. Furthermore, Il Sestante highlighted the importance of dedicated

housing services and local initiatives such as Padova per Abitanci, which combine mediation, legal and financial guidance, and pilot actions to promote affordable and inclusive access to housing.

Together, these proposals point toward a multi-level strategy combining grassroots mobilisation, coordinated advocacy, practical tools, structured landlord engagement, and continuous evaluation to strengthen access to housing and foster long-term systemic change.

Potential tools for replication and advocacy

- Several approaches piloted during the first phase show particular potential for replication or policy advocacy:
- Intergenerational co-housing models, connecting the needs of older residents with those of newcomers (Refugees Welcome Italia).
- Housing information points offering cultural mediation, translation support, and direct assistance with housing searches (ZRC SAZU).
- Integrated legal-financial support initiatives such as Padova per Abitanci, which combine mediation, guidance, and pilot activities to promote inclusive access to housing (Il Sestante).
- Register of Host Families (Albo delle Famiglie Accoglienti), providing an institutionally supported framework for sustained sponsor involvement.
- Multi-stakeholder housing working groups, ensuring continuity of coordination and institutional memory beyond the project cycle (Refugees Welcome Italia).
- Manifesto on anti-racist approaches to housing, aiming to promote housing accessibility, such as the anti-racist Manifesto for Padua.

Figure 13. Pilot activity developed in Padua, Italy

6. Key learnings and future roadmap

In the previous sections, we presented the main insights from the work carried out from March 2024 to September 2026. The data analyzed made it possible to assess the current status of the project in relation to its main objectives, as shown in Table 2. The table shows progress in achieving the project objectives.

In this section, we aim to highlight the main learnings and recommendations for the future. The learnings here presented are not a summary of activities completed, but a synthesis of the lessons that shaped implementation across six intervention territories (of the 8 partners of H:OUSE) in the first phase of the project. They are intended to both propose strategies that can be replicated in other projects and inform about the priorities for the second phase of the H:OUSE project as a roadmap.

6.1 Key learnings

- **Understanding the importance of diverse networks**

The first learning from the first phase of H:OUSE is that network creation is not a means to an end, but a significant outcome in itself. All partners expanded their networks, engaging a diverse range of actors, from diaspora communities and local volunteers to public institutions and private sector stakeholders. This expansion was shaped not only by the new connections formed during the project, but also by the relational infrastructure already in place prior to implementation. Partners with long-standing local roots could mobilise institutions and recruit diverse participants.

A key enabler of this engagement has been the diversity of the networks themselves. Across territories, partners observed that diversity attracts diversity: the presence of actors from different sectors and profiles within the same space generates a pull effect, drawing in others who would not have engaged in a more homogeneous setting. What motivates a participant is often precisely the ability to engage with others who approach the same challenge from different angles. When this cross-sectoral dimension is present, knowledge exchange becomes possible in ways that single-profile networks cannot replicate, and the network itself becomes a resource. Reaching this diversity, however, requires adapted strategies. Locally grounded engagement, multilingual communication, and the involvement of community leaders as bridges to newly arrived migrants were consistently highlighted as essential. Local leaders and diaspora representatives played a vital role not only in facilitating first contact, but in building the relational foundation necessary for sustained engagement over time.

Shared spaces were equally important in this regard. Informal settings such as cultural events, meals and coffee breaks enabled participants from a broad range of profiles to interact as equals, which fostered mutual trust and opened up opportunities for collaboration that more formal structures struggle to create. The involvement of local authorities and public institutions brought a further layer to this approach, lending

legitimacy to the project's activities and facilitating better coordination when addressing housing challenges.

However, building new networks is only part of the process; what was crucial in transforming those initial contacts into long-term partnerships was the ability to maintain them over time or, in other words, the continuity. This calls for regular follow-up, flexible planning and a shared objective established from the very beginning.

- **The role of integration in the indirect generation of housing solutions**

A central learning of the first phase is that, while H:OUSE does not provide direct financial support for housing solutions, such as rent subsidies or property acquisition, integration emerges as one of the most effective pathways to improving housing access for migrants and refugees.

Partners observed that barriers to housing are not only economic or structural, but also linguistic, cultural, administrative, and relational. Addressing these layers indirectly; through language learning focused on housing-related vocabulary and procedures, self-advocacy training, practical knowledge of rental markets, capacity building for sponsors, and campaigns against discrimination, contributes directly to expanding migrants' ability to navigate the housing system with greater autonomy and confidence.

The same logic applies to sponsors, whose capacity to support migrants depends on their own understanding of these barriers. Raising awareness among sponsors and equipping them with tools to act on that awareness proved equally important. Interactive and experiential methodologies such as role-plays, peer exchange, mentorship programmes, case studies, and co-design workshops proved more effective than conventional informational approaches in building empathy and consolidating practical housing knowledge. Crucially, the co-creation of activities reinforced participants' sense of ownership and motivation, which is essential to the long-term sustainability of the project's outcomes.

This points to a broader perspective, namely that the project's networking dimension and its integration dimension are closely intertwined. Based on the premise that stronger networks facilitate better integration, and better integration opens more housing pathways.

- **Advancing housing solutions through collective action**

The most significant and durable learning of the first phase concerns the shift in how housing is understood. At the outset of the project, many participants tended to frame housing difficulties as individual problems, to be solved through individual effort or case-by-case support. By the mid-term point, across multiple territories, a different understanding had taken hold: housing insecurity is a structural condition, rooted in broader urban, economic, and political dynamics, and it requires collective, coordinated responses.

This shift emerged through the knowledge-sharing processes; such as the ones developed in seminars, co-design sessions, participatory workshops, and informal exchanges, which created spaces for participants to reflect together, compare

experiences, and develop a shared analysis. Migrants came to understand that they are not alone in facing these challenges, while sponsors and local actors came to recognise that their support is not only relevant to migrants but to the broader conditions of housing access in their local territories. This reframing proved a necessary step toward the coordinated, rights-based responses that the project seeks to promote.

Crucially, partners also learned that migrants themselves must not feel alone in confronting this challenge. Ensuring that migrants move from a consultative role to becoming active participants and co-designers of solutions is essential both for the quality of the solutions developed and for the agency of those most affected.

Furthermore, when people understand housing insecurity as a shared structural problem, they are more likely to sustain engagement, take initiative within their own networks, and push for change beyond the scope of the project itself. In this sense, partners explicitly acknowledged that sustainable housing access requires structural public policy responses, including increased social housing investment, regulated rental markets and anti-discrimination enforcement, that fall outside the project's remit but must be named as necessary conditions for the work of projects like H:OUSE to have lasting effect.

The collective dimension, the emergence of a shared narrative and the growing willingness to act in a coordinated effort are the most important outcomes of the first phase of the H:OUSE project and, in turn, the ones most likely to endure once the project has concluded.

6.2 Roadmap – Next steps and priorities:

The following recommendations draw on the evidence and challenges documented across the six intervention territories during the first phase of H:OUSE. They identify the areas where the project's second phase should focus its attention in order to consolidate what has been built, address what has not yet been achieved, and strengthen the conditions for impact that extends beyond the project's scope.

- **Strengthening cross-sectoral engagement**

Participation across the different territories remains concentrated primarily within the public sector, NGOs, diaspora communities and local citizens. Broadening partnerships to include the private sector, such as banks, real estate agencies, and property owners, is therefore a priority for the second phase of H:OUSE.

For achieving that purpose, greater institutional involvement through formal public calls for proposals could provide the legitimacy and visibility needed to attract private participation. However, this approach depends on a level of political commitment that has not yet been secured in most territories.

- **Consolidating spaces for knowledge sharing**

Knowledge exchanges between sponsors have not occurred uniformly across all implementation territories. In part, this reflects the fact that several initiatives were still in a consolidation phase at the time of this report. Activities focused on knowledge

sharing have strengthened trust and relationships but have not yet consistently translated into concrete operational outcomes. The second phase would be focused not only on maintaining the spaces for exchange already created, but on deepening them, moving from relationship-building toward shared coordinated action.

- **Project continuity beyond the funding cycle**

The second phase should treat network continuity as a priority. This means identifying which partnerships have the greatest potential to continue beyond the project's formal duration and working to embed them within existing institutions or support their legal and financial independence. The relationships and working groups built through H:OUSE already function as informal coordination mechanisms; the goal for the second phase is to give the most promising of these a more stable foundation so that the progress may extend beyond the duration of the project.

6.3 Objectives of the project

The following table maps the project's five core objectives against the activities carried out, the previewed activities in the project, the outcomes and an assessment of progress to date. It draws on the evidence presented in Sections 3, 4, and 5 to identify, for each objective, what has been achieved and what requires further attention in the second phase. Items marked in red indicate areas where evidence remains incomplete or where additional data collection is needed prior to finalisation of this report.

Figure 14. Pilot activity, Padua, Italy

Objectives	Activities What will the project do to achieve the goals?	Outcomes What are the effects, results or impacts of the project?	Assessment of progress What are the indicators that still need to be achieved?
(a) Expand knowledge on the topic of Community Sponsorship, to explore and capitalize on the most successful experiences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Engage 100 diaspora community representatives through meetings - Produce a comprehensive scientific report on cross-dimensional research 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 239 participations (40 diaspora orgs) - Improved understanding of housing as a structural issue (see Section 3 – Knowledge Sharing) - Cross dimensional research published - Better awareness of migrant challenges and CS initiatives 	<p>Far from the expected: 40 representatives of the diaspora communities engaged</p> <p>Strong attitudinal shift thanks to knowledge sharing (Section 3) indicates good progress.</p>
(b) Expand and diversify the pool of sponsors and individuals directly involved in the support and integration of migrants and asylum seekers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Engage at least 70 sponsors (20% new), measured by registration and participation - Use innovative recruitment strategies focused on economic benefits, evaluated through feedback - Provide capacity-building through training, assessed via learning tests and feedback - Offer support services, evaluated by resource quality and sponsor satisfaction 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 425 participants; 81 new sponsors (27%) → target exceeded - Improved skills, attitudes, and engagement - Participants from 63 different nationalities, with 5 entries from people with dual nationality. - Gender balance: 53% of participants were women and 47% men - Diverse age in participants - Stronger links with migrant communities (see Section 2 – Network Connections) 	<p>Target exceeded 81 new sponsors from the 70 provide indicates good progress</p> <p>Good diversity metrics</p> <p>Needs strengthening: engagement of private stakeholders.</p>
(c) Support and empower local sponsor communities by consolidating a support structure that includes all those actors (public and private) that play a role of relevance, impact and decision-making around the dynamics of access to housing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Establish 20 multistakeholder networks, measured by the number of entities involved and frequency of interactions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Networks and co-design processes established (see Sections 2 and 3) - Institutional engagement achieved (see Section 2) 	<p>15 networks out of the 20 that are expected</p> <p>Needs strengthening: engagement of private stakeholders.</p>
(d) Develop and implement innovative and concrete housing solutions for people in need of international protection, through the establishment of the local multi-stakeholder groups	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Implement pilot housing activities, measured by community involvement and success 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increased knowledge on housing issues (Section 4 – Housing Solutions) - Pilot models tested (co-housing, mediation, legal/financial support, databases) 	<p>Progress evident (Section 4), but initiatives remain at an intermediate stage.</p>
(e) Expand the number of Member States running CS programmes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Conduct meetings with policymakers to promote CS programmes. - Organize forums and roundtables with stakeholders - Strengthen collaborations between European organizations and learning between existing and potential adopters. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Improved cross-border collaboration - Transnational meeting in Ioannina - AMIF meetings and working group in Italy - APDR Congress 	<p>Progress observed in the cooperation with other AMIF projects, seminars, international meetings, but expected outputs not fully evidenced in this report stage.</p> <p>Needs strengthening: dissemination and expansion to other EU territories.</p>

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ASPETTATIVE

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CONTRIBUTI

“I realised that housing is not only about physical space, but about building community and mutual support. Developing intergenerational exchange systems can help tackle multiple social challenges simultaneously.”

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H:OUSE